

Ameliorative Effect of Selenium on Gastrointestinal Damages Following Oral Administration of Indomethacin in Male Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are commonly used for the treatment of pain and inflammation; however, their use is associated with gastrointestinal injury. Selenium, an essential trace mineral involved in several physiological functions, plays an important role in redox balance and possesses antioxidant properties. This study investigated the effect of selenium on gastrointestinal damage following subacute administration of indomethacin. Twenty male Wistar rats weighing 200–250 g were randomly divided into four groups of five rats each. Group 1 served as the control, while Groups 2, 3, and 4 received indomethacin at 5 mg/kg daily. In addition, Groups 3 and 4 received selenium at 2 mg/kg and omeprazole at 20 mg/kg, respectively. All treatments were administered orally for seven days, after which the animals were sacrificed. Blood samples were collected for the determination of TNF- α and NF- κ B levels, while stomach and colon tissues were harvested for the assessment of oxidative stress and antioxidant parameters. The results showed that stomach and colon levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were significantly increased in the indomethacin-treated group, accompanied by significant reductions in total antioxidant capacity (TAC), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and reduced glutathione (GSH). Administration of selenium and omeprazole significantly reversed these alterations. Similarly, serum levels of TNF- α and NF- κ B were significantly elevated in the indomethacin group compared with the control group, whereas selenium and omeprazole significantly attenuated these increases. Selenium also significantly increased gastric catalase activity compared with the indomethacin-only group. These findings suggest that oral administration of selenium may be beneficial in ameliorating NSAID-induced gastrointestinal oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue injury.

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Introduction

Gastrointestinal dysfunction comprises of several disorders of the digestive system and these include: gastric ulcer, ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease (1). These diseases are usually accompanied by oxidative stress and inflammation at the initial stage and can eventually lead to death (2). Most of these gastrointestinal disorders are caused by the effect of certain substances, which could be food, drugs, gas effluents, pathogens, etc (3).

Despite the various aetiologies of the gastrointestinal dysfunction, the major cause over the years has been associated with the use of drugs, especially the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) (4). NSAIDs are a group of drugs, widely used in the treatment of inflammation and pain (5). However, research has shown that NSAIDs can induce gastrointestinal complications, thereby potentiating their toxicity (4) Indomethacin is a NSAIDs that is capable of causing serious adverse effects in the

gastrointestinal system when used in an uncontrolled manner (6).

Selenium is an essential trace mineral that is crucial for various bodily functions, including the proper functioning of the immune system (7). It plays a vital role in redox balancing, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities (8). It has been reported to help maintain redox balance by neutralizing the reactive oxygen species (ROS) and protecting immune cells from oxidative damage (9). It also exerts anti-inflammatory effects by regulating the production of inflammatory cytokines (10). Moreover, the anti-inflammatory and antioxidant actions of sub-acute orally administered selenium on indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal dysfunction have not been largely defined. This study, therefore, aimed at investigating the ameliorative effect of selenium on gastrointestinal disorders in male Wistar rats.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals: Indomethacin capsule was purchased from Ningbo DHY Pharma Co., Ltd., China; Selenium was gotten from Molychem, India; Omeprazole capsule was purchased from Xi'an ZB Biotech Co., Ltd., China.

Experimental Animals

Twenty (20) male Wistar rats, weighing 200-250g were used for the study. They were housed in cages, in a well-ventilated animal house of the Department of Physiology, Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA); they were given free access to rat pellets and water ad libitum. They were acclimatized for two weeks prior the experimentation. The experimental procedure was carried out in accordance with the guidelines of Centre for Research and Development (CERAD), Federal University of Technology, Akure, ethical number assigned: FUTA/ETH/24/136.

Experimental design

The animals were randomly divided into four groups of five animals each (n=5). Group 1 (control) received normal saline only; groups 2, 3 and 4 received indomethacin at a dose of 5mg/kg dissolved in 5% sodium bicarbonate; group 3 also received selenium at a dose of 2mg/kg dissolved in normal saline, while group 4 also received omeprazole at a dose of 20 mg/kg dissolved in distilled water. After acclimatization, the animals were made to fast for 24 hours before the first dose of indomethacin administration. Group 3 received selenium 2 hours after the first dose of indomethacin, while Group 4, received omeprazole within the same period, being a standard group. The animals were thereafter given access to feed and water ad libitum. The administration was done concurrently for 7 days. Prior to the day of sacrifice, the animals were fasted for 24 hours and were sacrificed.

Collection of Blood and Organs

The stomach and colon were excised and divided into two sections; a section was stored in 2ml of ice-cold 0.1 M Tris potassium chloride (Tris KCl) buffer, pH 7.4, for biochemical assays. The second section was preserved in buffered formalin for histological analysis. Furthermore, the blood samples were collected through the retro-orbital sinus into plain bottles for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The blood samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes to obtain the serum samples.

Biochemical assays

The stomach and colon samples stored in Tris-KCl buffer were homogenized and the resultant homogenates were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The supernatants post mitochondrial fraction

was collected and processed for biochemical experimental procedures.

Determination of Protein concentration

The protein concentrations of the various samples were determined by means of the Biuret method as described by Gornal et al., (1949) with a slight modification of adding potassium iodide to the reagent to prevent precipitation of Cu^{2+} ions as cuprous oxide.

Determination of Malondialdehyde levels (MDA)

Malondialdehyde (MDA) a marker of lipid peroxidation was determined by measuring the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) produced during lipid peroxidation. This was carried out by the method of Varshney and Kale (1990).

Determination of Total nitrite

Nitrite determination was done using the method described by Ignarro *et al.*, 1987. The assay relies on a diazotization reaction that was originally described by Griess in 1879.

Determination of hydrogen peroxide

Hydrogen peroxide generation was determined according to the method of Wolff (1994).

Determination of superoxide dismutase activity (SOD)

The level of SOD activity was determined by the method of Misra and Fridovich (1972).

Determination of Catalase activity

Catalase activity was determined according to the method of Sinha (1972).

Determination of Reduced Glutathione levels (GSH)

The method of Beutler (1963) was followed in estimating the level of GSH.

Determination of Total Antioxidant Capacity

Total antioxidant capacity was determined according to the method described by Rubio *et al.* (2016).

Determination of Tumour Necrosis Factor (TNF- α) and Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B)

Tumour Necrosis Factor alpha (TNF- α) and Nuclear Factor Kappa B (NF- κ B) were determined using a colourimetric assay with kits purchased from Cloud-Clone Corp with the instruction manual followed appropriately.

Statistical Analysis

The results were expressed as Mean \pm SEM, and statistical evaluation was made using GraphPad Prism version 9.5. The differences across groups were assessed by means of analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons test for post-hoc comparison of group means. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results

Figure 1: Effect of selenium on total protein and malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

Figure 1A and 1B represent the total protein concentration in the stomach and colon, respectively. There was no significant difference in the protein concentration across the groups in both organs. The MDA concentration of both the stomach and colon is presented in Figures 1C and 1D, and they were both significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg group

compared to the control. The MDA concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group compared to the Indo 5mg/kg group in both stomach and colon samples. The Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group was significantly increased in the colon compared with the control.

Figure 1: Effect of selenium on protein and malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- Protein concentration of stomach, B- Protein concentration of Colon, C- MDA concentration of stomach, D- MDA concentration of colon) Values are presented as Mean \pm SEM, *Significant difference at $p < 0.05$ compared with control, # significant difference at $p < 0.05$ when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Figure 2: Effect of selenium on nitric oxide (NO) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) concentration in the

stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

Figure 2A and 2B represent the effect of selenium on NO concentration in the stomach and colon, respectively. A significant decrease in the NO concentration of the stomach was observed in Indo 5mg/kg compared to the control. However, the NO concentration of the colon was significantly increased in Indo 5mg/kg compared with the control. A significant decrease in the NO concentration of the colon was observed in both Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg compared to the Indo 5mg/kg group.

The effect of selenium on H₂O₂ concentration in the stomach and colon is shown in Figures 2C and 2D. H₂O₂ concentration was significantly increased in the

Indo 5mg/kg group compared to the control group in both organs. In the stomach (Fig 2C), H₂O₂ concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group compared with both the Indo 5mg/kg and control groups, respectively; and significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg group compared with the control group. In the colon sample (Fig 2D), the H₂O₂ concentration was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg group compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group; the concentration of H₂O₂ in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg group was significantly increased compared with the control.

Figure 2: Effect of selenium on nitric oxide (NO) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) concentration in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- Nitric oxide concentration of stomach, B- Nitric oxide concentration of colon, C- H₂O₂ concentration of stomach, D- H₂O₂ concentration of colon)

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p < 0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p < 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Figure 3: Effect of selenium on superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase activity in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

The results for SOD activity in the stomach and colon are shown in Figure 3A and 3B, respectively. The

activity of SOD was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both organs. In the stomach (Fig 3A), the SOD activity of Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg was significantly increased compared with the control and Indo 5 mg/kg groups, respectively; however, it was significantly decreased

in Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg compared with both the control and Indo 5mg/kg groups. The SOD activity of the Indo 5mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg groups was significantly decreased in the colon (Fig 3B) compared with the control. Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg was significantly increased compared with Indo 5mg/kg.

Catalase activity is shown in Figures 3C and 3D. Catalase activity was significantly increased in the selenium group compared to both the control and indomethacin groups in the stomach, while other groups were insignificant. More so, it was insignificantly increased across all groups in the colon (Fig 3D).

Figure 3: Effect of selenium on Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) and catalase activity in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- SOD activity of stomach, B- SOD activity of colon, C- Catalase activity of stomach, D- Catalase activity of colon)

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p< 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Figure 4: Effect of selenium on Reduced Glutathione (GSH) and Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) in the stomach and colon following indomethacin administration

Figure 4A and 4B represent the effect of selenium on reduced glutathione (GSH) in the stomach and colon, respectively. The GSH was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both organs. Moreover, the GSH activity of Indo

5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg groups was significantly increased compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group in both organs.

The TAC, as represented in figures 4C and 4D, was significantly decreased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control in both the stomach and colon. However, it was significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome

20mg/kg groups compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group and the control group in both organs.

Figure 4: Effect of selenium on Reduced Glutathione (GSH) and Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) in stomach and colon following indomethacin administration (A- GSH of stomach, B- GSH of colon, C- TAC of stomach, D- TAC of colon)

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p< 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Table 1: Effect of selenium on tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-α) and nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB) in blood serum following indomethacin administration Table 1 shows the effect of selenium on TNF-α and NF-κB in blood serum following indomethacin administration. Both TNF-α and NF-κB were

significantly increased in the Indo 5mg/kg group compared with the control. However, they were significantly decreased in Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg and Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg groups compared with the Indo 5mg/kg group.

Groups	TNF-a (pg/ml/mg protein)	NF-kB (pg/ml/mg protein)
Control	56.00±6.012	140.00±10.91
Indo 5mg/kg	114.00±10.34*	189.80±12.33*
Indo 5mg/kg + Sel 2mg/kg	58.04±4.01#	117.0±2.20#
Indo 5mg/kg + Ome 20mg/kg	70.56±4.00#	108.40±3.59#

Values are presented as Mean ± SEM, *Significant difference at p<0.05 compared with control, # significant difference at p< 0.05 when compared with Indo 5mg/kg

Discussion

Selenium is a trace element that has been reported to possess anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties at a low dose (8, 11). Indomethacin, on the other hand, has been linked to gastrointestinal damages which is characterized by increased ROS and inflammation (12). The increased length and time between doses are factors responsible for its harmful effect (13). This is indicated by the increased MDA and H₂O₂ levels in the indomethacin group in the organs affected. Coupled with this effect is the presentation of decreased antioxidant enzymes in the indomethacin group. However, this study has shown potential anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of selenium by activating certain antioxidant enzymes which act as scavengers against the free radicals (14).

The increased MDA and H₂O₂ levels observed in the indomethacin group of both organs are attributed to the capability of indomethacin in the alteration of the gastrointestinal system's integrity (15), and this is due to its ability to induce lipid peroxidation (16). On the contrary, the reduced levels of MDA and H₂O₂ in the selenium group of both organs demonstrated its antioxidant property in reversing oxidative damage caused by peroxides and other free radicals. This result corresponds to a previous study, which showed that selenium in combination with other vitamins suppresses oxidative stress (17).

Total antioxidant capacity is an assay used to measure antioxidant levels and the status of ROS in the system, not necessarily assessing individual antioxidant enzymes (8). The significant reduction in TAC observed in the indomethacin-treated group suggests depletion of endogenous antioxidant reserves and disruption of redox homeostasis resulting from excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation (18). Conversely, selenium supplementation markedly increased TAC, indicating restoration of antioxidant defenses. This observation is consistent with recent evidence demonstrating that selenium enhances antioxidant capacity through its incorporation into selenoproteins, including glutathione peroxidases and thioredoxin reductases, which play crucial roles in ROS detoxification and maintenance of cellular redox balance (19, 20). Additionally, enzymes like SOD and GSH are inhibited by indomethacin in affected organs, but are reversed by selenium. This effect is likely due to selenium's potential to protect membrane lipids and macromolecules from oxidative damage caused by free radicals. The remarkable effectiveness of selenium in the stomach supports previous research suggesting that selenium can enhance the organ's antioxidant status (21).

Nitric oxide (NO) is a multifunctional signalling molecule that plays a dual role in gastrointestinal physiology and inflammation. While physiological concentrations of NO contribute to mucosal defence, vascular homeostasis, and epithelial integrity, excessive NO production, particularly through inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), promotes inflammatory responses and tissue injury (22). Mechanistically, NO modulates inflammation through complex interactions with the NF- κ B signaling pathway, a key regulator of pro-inflammatory gene expression (23). Depending on its concentration and cellular redox state, NO may either activate or suppress NF- κ B-mediated inflammatory responses. Furthermore, NO can react with cysteine sulfhydryl (-SH) residues of target proteins, resulting in S-nitrosylation, a post-translational modification capable of altering protein function and attenuating NF- κ B activation (24). In pathological conditions, excess NO readily reacts with superoxide anions (O₂⁻) to generate peroxynitrite (ONOO⁻), a highly reactive oxidant that contributes to oxidative damage, lipid peroxidation, and cellular dysfunction (25). Consistent with these mechanisms, the present study demonstrated elevated NO levels in the colon of indomethacin-treated animals, suggesting enhanced nitric oxide-mediated stress and inflammatory activity. Conversely, NO levels were reduced in the stomach, which may reflect impairment of its gastroprotective functions, including maintenance of mucosal blood flow, mucus secretion, and epithelial restitution. Selenium supplementation significantly attenuated colonic NO elevation, likely through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions mediated by selenoproteins such as glutathione peroxidases and thioredoxin reductases, which limit reactive oxygen species generation and downstream inflammatory signalling (23). In the stomach, selenium treatment further modulated NO levels, potentially contributing to preservation of mucosal integrity and protection against indomethacin-induced gastric injury.

Indomethacin induces inflammation by affecting NF- κ B, a protein that is responsible for the expression of adhesion molecules such as Intercellular Adhesion Molecule 1 (ICAM-1). A pro-inflammatory cytokine known as TNF- α is involved in NSAIDs-induced damage by contributing to the increment of ICAM-1 and thereby potentiating inflammatory response (26). More so, it increases intracellular oxidative stress. The findings of this study have shown the effectiveness of selenium in ameliorating damage caused by the actions of the inflammatory cytokine (NF- κ B) (27). This will lead to decreased production of pro-

inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α . This aligns with the findings of Mal'tseva and colleagues, in that selenium regulates the activities of inflammatory cytokines through direct oxidation of critical sulfhydryl groups of the transcription factor (10). Moreover, this anti-inflammatory effect could also be a result of the presence of seleno S, a type of selenoprotein responsible for producing anti-inflammatory mediators (1).

The observations and inferences made from this study have contributed to the previous research that selenium has both anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties against indomethacin-induced gastrointestinal damage, and its effectiveness is based on the ability to activate antioxidant enzymes and regulate inflammatory cytokines at low doses.

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